

Effect of the caries on the mechanical properties of the tooth and direct effect on the pulp. Novel introductory models to lighten possible pathway of repair dentine build up

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Abstract

Carious teeth entitle large loss of the material that lead to different response to loads. Odontoblast will act as a strain gauge that will be affected by the deformation of the pulp tissues resulted from the exaggerated deformation of the dentinal tooth frame. Stiffness of the tooth structure will affect the pulp response. In this paper we want to introduce this mechanical concepts.

Keywords: dentine, Biomechanics, dental pulp, ankylotic teeth, stiffness of tooth, strain gauge, dental caries, numerical simulation.

Introduction

Dental caries in many instances associated with repair. This repair had been attributed in many instances to the chemical notorious stimulation of the pulp from the weakened and leaky dentine wall. Odontoblast had 2 main features that making them the best sensor to sense any change in the stiffness of the dentine

- Their interconnectivity via specialized complex molecular pathway (1)
- Their mechanical arrangement via
 - o Pre-dentine space
 - o Unique process of the odontoblast process (2). Where this articular feature is directly involved in the deposition of the new layers of the intratubular dentine.
 - o The intercellular connection had also suggested mechanical aspect. Where this feature is related to the deposition of the secondary and tertiary dentine as well as repair dentine.

This picture had a close resemblance to the osteocytes, but in the case of osteocyte we had well established and identified role in the bone physiology (3). Many numerical models had depicted this matter (4). This thesis on the odontoblasts effect as part of the dental pulp needs a numerical model to represent it. As the osteocyte had a well-known role and this role is well correlated to the numerical model, we could apply these criteria to the odontoblast, dental pulp and dentinal repair an addition to the deposition of the secondary dentine.

Mechanical sensing action of the odontoblast had been well studied (5), but this is the first time a numerical model had been introduced

Carious tooth model

Figure 1 this is a simple 2D represented an intact and carious model

According to our knowledge, what causes the dental pulp to form the secondary, tertiary or the reparative dentine is the change in the strain distribution in the dental structure that will be sensed by the pulp tissues which start to respond accordingly. We had done model with solid pup to see the possible effect of changed stresses distribution in the dentine on the pulp

Figure 2 Pulpal dentin junction. 1) outside tooth/enamel 2) dentin tubule 3) dentin 4) odontoblastic process 5) pre-dentin 6) odontoblast 7) capillaries 8) fibroblasts 9) nerve 10) artery/vein 11) cell-rich zone 12) cell-poor zone 13) pulp chamber. All previous arrangements had a specialized mechanical arm

Methods

Figure 3 this is our model

The used model was simplified. The bone and dentine were assigned to properties closer to the PMMA. The dental pulp and PD ligaments had a very soft nature. When we model the pulp via a solid entity, we want to estimate the response of the pulp. We had modeled the pulp like the PD tissue, very soft, although both have different mechanical responses. The orthodontic brackets were modeled as ceramic brackets. Although the ceramic brackets have less popularity than metallic analogue, their mechanical properties make them highly stiff rendering the results better to serve our goals.

Results and discussions

In the case of tooth model, we want to investigate these criteria

- Effect of the carries on the pulp via static analysis. We had considered *mastication* is a static event and the pulp was solid in this case. The caries was very close to the pulp. The connection between the pulp and inner wall of the dentine is unique across all body connections, and needs special biomechanical attention.
- Effect of trauma

Enamel is very important to be stiffer than dentine. Next model is trauma response if enamel like enamel. Enamel produces an important feature of the stiffens gradient determination. The next model will depict this effect in a very simple way, namely displacement graph

Figure 4 This model is the trauma responses if enamel is like enamel. Next model is trauma response if enamel like dentine.

Figure 5 The model is trauma response if enamel like dentine. Next models are for No carious tooth strain energy density.

Figure 6 This is the non-carious mode. As we want to investigate the effect on the pulp from deformation we

Figure 7 This is the non-carious model strain energy of the pulp

Figure 8 Non-carious model other view. Current and previous models are for No carious tooth strain energy density.

Next models for simple caries tooth

Figure 9 This is the strain energy density of the pulp of the non-carious model. Caries outline is apparent

The carious had been simulated as a smooth defect although this is oversimplification in addition the correlation of the carious lesion progression should be correlated with the mechanical loading of the tooth. The orthotropic tooth structure should be reviewed with the progression of the carious lesion as well.

Figure 10 This is the strain energy density of the pulp of the carious model

Figure 11 Carious model in another model. The carious lesion is done in an engineering way which makes it more parametric.

Figure 12 Previous models for simple caries models. Next models are for more extensive caries.

Figure 13 This model is for more extensive caries.

Figure 14 This model is for more extensive caries from another view.

Figure 15 This model is for more extensive caries from another view. Many models had not been analyzed thoroughly.

Previous models are for more extensive caries. The interface between the pulp and dentine is very important to be considered when analyzing the model. Next are models for more extensive caries but with no direct bond between the pulp and the dentine.

Figure 16 This model is for more extensive caries.

Figure 17 This model is for more extensive caries from another view.

Figure 18 Previous models are for more extensive caries but with no direct bond between the pulp and the dentine.

The reality is a gradient between the bonded and non-bonded status. Next model is to show the dynamic tooth response to the trauma. First model is the solid non voided dentine to show the importance of the pulp chamber to the performance of the teeth. The pulp also plays significant role in the modification of the teeth response.

Dentine must always be seen as a modifiable non remodelable while bone is modifiable remodelable material. Both are composite. Both are composed mainly from collagen fibers.

Fibers orientations are totally different in the name of orthotropicity

The strain energy density had been clearly altered in the carious model which have a high close connection to the bone model as well as the same process of the dentine repair. Current model could be an explanation of the part of the repair process. The repair pathways is highly complicated but this mechanical arm should be deeply investigated for further refinement and validation.

Figure 19 Dynamic response of the solid non-pulped tooth model

A dynamic response represents a trauma case. Our trauma boundary timing in all studied models is the same. Whenever we have a different setting, we will denote for that.

Figure 20 This model is the solid non voided dentine

The previous model is the solid non voided dentine to show the importance of the pulp chamber to the performance of the teeth. Next model is the voided dentine to show the importance of the pulp chamber to the performance of the teeth.

Figure 21 This is the pulped model in dynamic response.

Figure 22 This is the pulped (voided) model in dynamic response.

The previous model is the voided dentine to show the importance of the pulp chamber to the performance of the teeth. It contains pulp tissue. To compare its response to the same model we had to do analysis for both models and compare with them. Next is static analysis of the voided model without pulp tissue with slow force.

Figure 23 Static analysis of the voided model without pulp tissue with slow force

Previous static analysis of the voided model without pulp tissue with slow force. Next is the static analysis of the voided model with pulp tissue with slow force.

Figure 24 Static analysis of the voided model with pulp tissue with slow force.

Previous static analysis of the voided model with pulp tissue with slow force. Voided dentine model had not been affected by the presence of the pulp model on the slow force, which means both models are equal but this needs finer tuning based upon the physical model. We should emphasize that the living tissues processing will affect their mechanical properties totally. We had not done a dynamic analysis comparison which is prudent

to be done, although we don't anticipate that pulp will affect the digital model response or the real model tooth whether static or dynamic conditions are faced. The presence of the dentinal tubules plays a significant modulation of the response of the dentine. Next model is the non-pulped model, but the dentine contains the dentinal tubules.

Figure 25 Pulpless model with dentinal tubules

Figure 26 the dentinal tubules are apparent

The FEA and virtual analysis setting provide the researchers with very powerful tools. In the previous model the toggling of the transparency of all parts apart from the dentine gives us an insight into the response of the dentine. Although we had not agreed about a model that is close enough to represent the dentine, we could regard this model as a clue to approach a more parametric way. The previous model is the non-pulped model, but the dentine contains the dentinal tubules.

Next is the non-tubuled tooth for comparison with the previous model.

Figure 27 Non tubular dentine

To reveal the effect of the tubules we had to compare Y field displacement between the tubule model and the non-tubuled model.

Figure 28 Tubuled model

Figure 29 Non-tubuled model

Non-tubuled model. It is worth noticing that the time to reach maximum value in different fields is different. It is also prudent to remember always that these responses are between specific parts of the anatomical structure and the different parameters had not been studied simultaneously due the limitation of the current hardware resources.

In our previously published paper, we had demonstrated clearly the effect of the PD passively on the alveolar process.

(6) In this paper we will demonstrate the effect of

- 1- absence of PD ligament
- 2- nature of the tooth and titanium dental implants on the stress transfer from the tooth or implant to the alveolar bone

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Author profile

Mohammed Zahid Saadoon BDS– FKHCMS (Maxillofacial Surgery). During 2014-2024 he was involved in many researches in biomechanics and biomechatronic. He developed many theories in maxillofacial traumatology, craniofacial growth and dental implantology. He developed a unique dental implant system. He has a special interest in mechanical engineering applications in the medical and dental specialties as well as in forensic medicine. He is now working as maxillofacial surgeon in Ashty teaching hospital, largest secondary referral centers in Soran discrete at Kurdistan region / Iraq.